

Versatile Seebeck and Electrical Resistivity measurement setup for thin films

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A custom setup for Seebeck coefficient and Electrical resistivity measurements of thin films as a function of temperature in the range of [10 – 300] K was developed. The Seebeck coefficient is measured using a two-probe arrangement and in either a dynamical or steady/quasi-steady differential method. The temperature differences (ΔT s) for these measurements across the samples are achieved by using resistive heaters embedded in two copper blocks. The sample is screwed to these blocks and is in pressured contact with the measurement probes. The electrical resistivity is measured with a two-probe arrangement. To verify the reliability of the developed setup, measurement tests were performed on commercial niobium foil and specular spin valve previously studied, having obtained a great accordance (within $\sim 3\%$) between this setup's experimental results and the reference measurements.

I. INTRODUCTION

The thermoelectric effects (Seebeck and Peltier) are phenomena that convert heat into electricity or vice-versa, respectively¹. Even though these effects have been discovered several years ago, contemporary thermoelectric materials are gaining more attention due to their possible applications in power generation, heat recovery and electronic refrigeration, besides the common application to temperature measurements²⁻⁶. Moreover, by being effects solely based on non-equilibrium carrier transport, their study also allows for insights into novel materials such as topological insulators⁷, 2D materials^{8, 9}, and magnetocaloric materials^{10, 11}. These can be key materials for several breakthroughs in, for example, energy harvesting and spintronics^{12, 13}, among others. All these applications and ground-breaking materials research create the need of a reliable, fast and easy to perform measurement of the Seebeck coefficient (thermopower) S , given by $S = - \lim_{\Delta T \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\Delta V}{\Delta T} \right)$.

For applications in energy harvesting, the thermoelectric materials are also evaluated by the figure of merit ZT , $ZT = \alpha T / k$, with k the thermal conductivity and α the power factor given by $\alpha = S^2 / \rho$, with ρ the resistivity. Thus, the coupling of S and ρ measurements is crucial. Having the power factor, the output power of thermoelectric materials can be assessed without performing the complex measurement of the thermal conductivity^{14, 15}. Moreover, by combining the measurements of these two transport properties, insights into the band structure of the material can be obtained. By this means, the study of novel

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exotic materials is attained by measuring these two properties, creating the demand for a simple resistivity and Seebeck coefficient measurement.

However, even though the measurement of the thermopower and of the resistivity seem to be simple processes, obtained by applying a temperature difference or current and measuring the generated voltage, the realization and production of reliable results is still difficult, especially as a function of temperature for low temperatures^{14, 16-21}. Two Seebeck coefficient measurement techniques have been widely studied and explored: the differential and the integral method²². In the differential method, several small temperature differences (ΔT s) are applied to the sample and the corresponding thermoelectric voltage is obtained. Usually, this method is employed in a steady-state, where each voltage measurement is only performed after a ΔT stabilization, which is time consuming for measurements as a function of temperature^{23, 24}. These measurements can also be performed in a quasi-steady state, without waiting for ΔT to stabilize. In the integral method, one end of the sample is kept at a fixed temperature and the opposite temperature is varied continuously, with the Seebeck coefficient being calculated from the generated voltage²⁵.

Most measurements of the Seebeck coefficient and resistivity of a thin film are also achieved by drawing contacts on top of the thin film. This can be achieved either manually^{26, 27} or by using complex processes, such as lithography²⁸⁻³¹ and wire bonding^{18, 20, 32-34}. By drawing manually, several issues can arise. The size of the contacts is one of the biggest issues for measurements of metallic thin films' resistivities. The use of lithography solves this issue and allows the creation of differential thermocouples and local heaters for a Seebeck coefficient measurement. On the other hand, lithography can also be too time consuming and expensive. Thus, the measurement of these transport properties in thin films is still a challenge.

In this paper, we present a measurement setup of the Seebeck coefficient for thin films at temperatures in the range [10 – 300] K. A dynamic differential method can be employed to obtain a fast measurement of the Seebeck coefficient as a function of temperature. Moreover, a steady and/or quasi-steady state method can also be employed. Using the same apparatus, the resistivity can also be measured by a two-probe method, within the same range of temperatures. The details of the instrumentation and implementation are described and to validate the reliability and accuracy of the setup, test measurements on certain materials were performed.

II. PRINCIPLE AND SETUP

A. Measurement apparatus

The measurement apparatus is represented in Figure 1.a). A closed cycle cryostat (APD Cryogenics Inc. system, HC-4 MK1 compressor) with operating temperatures between 10 and 300 K is used. The measurement setup described in the next subsection could also be used in other cryostats and/or ovens with operating temperatures between 5 K and 473.15 K. The

sample chamber is evacuated prior to any measurements to a pressure of 9×10^{-6} mbar using an oil diffusion pump backed up by a rotary mechanical pump. At the end of the second stage copper cold head, the homemade sample holder, which contains the measurement setup, can be mounted. Indium foil is used for better thermal contact with the cold head. To this second stage, a Chromel/AuFe thermocouple (TCA) and heater are attached and are connected to a Lakeshore 331 temperature controller, which allows for a PID feedback control loop of the temperature of the second stage and ultimately of the sample holder.

A primary radiation shield, polished to mirror finish both on the inner and outer surfaces, attaches to the second stage copper cold head. A secondary radiation shield is mounted on the first stage of the cold head. All probe wires are twisted around the first and second stages of the cold head and held with Teflon tape, to ensure good thermal anchoring. This electrical feedthrough of the cryostat is connected to all the instrumentation devices via a twisted air round cable.

B. Measurement setup

A digital photograph and sketch of the measurement setup is represented in Figure 1.b), and c). The measurement setup is mounted on a copper sample holder. In this holder, two copper blocks are assembled on top of GE varnish embedded shroud paper. This guarantees a good thermal contact and at the same time electric insulation. The ΔT s can be generated by Joule heating of a copper (Cu) 53Ω resistance inside the copper blocks. Two probe wires are coupled to the blocks. One corresponds to the differential thermocouples (Type T) of each block (TC1 and TC2), having as reference the copper sample holder temperature. The other probes (Cu wires), one on each block, measure the voltage generated across the sample and feed the current for resistivity measurements. The sample is placed on top of the two blocks, which hold an empty space of 2.5×0.5 cm, corresponding to the maximum size of a sample to be measured. Two copper bars held together by two screws each are also attached to hold the sample to the blocks and to ensure the electrical pressured contact of the sample with the probes. A Chromel/AuFe thermocouple (TCB), having 0°C as reference, is inserted into the sample holder after its installation in the second stage cold head. It measures the sample holder temperature, which is the blocks and sample temperature if no ΔT s are applied, due to the ensured good thermal contacts.

FIGURE 1: Setup and Sample Holder. a) A photograph of the sample holder and the setup mounted onto the cryostat without the radiation shields. b) Detailed photograph of the setup. c) Sketch of the side view of the setup.

The voltage across the sample and the differential thermocouple voltage of one block (TC2) is measured by a Keithley 2182 Nanovoltmeter, using Channel 1 and 2, respectively. The differential thermocouple voltage of the other block (TC1) is measured by a Keithley 182 Nanovoltmeter. The thermocouple voltage of the sample holder (TCB) is measured by an Agilent 3458A 8½ Digit Multimeter. The current for generating a temperature difference and for the resistivity measurements is applied using a Time Electronics Current Source 9818. Using an IEEE 488.2 GPIB communication bus, all the instruments interface with a computer, where custom developed NI LabVIEW programs automate the procedures and collect the measurements results.

B. Measurement procedure

The setup described in the previous section allows for the measurement of both the Seebeck coefficient and Electrical Resistivity as a function of temperature in the range [10 – 300] K.

1. Seebeck coefficient measurement

The Seebeck coefficient is measured in a two-probe arrangement, with the versatility of measuring in a dynamic or a steady and/or quasi-steady differential method.

Dynamic measurement

For a faster and reliable Seebeck coefficient measurement, the dynamic method can be used, except in the case of materials with phase transitions. In this method, the temperature of the sample holder is varied at a constant rate of 0.5 K/min, with each thermal cycle lasting 20 hours, and it is monitored by the TCA and TCB thermocouples. A constant current is applied to the heating resistance of Block 1 to establish the ΔT . The temperature of Block 1, which is the temperature of one side of the sample, is measured by the thermocouple TC1. In these conditions, the temperature of Block 2 is kept equal to the

temperature of the sample holder ($TC2 = TCB$) and varied at the same rate. By applying a current, the temperature of Block 1 will always remain higher than TCB . ΔT (equal to the difference between $TC1$ and $TC2$) does not remain constant during the measurement, due to the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of copper and of the sample. In Figure 2, the variation of ΔT as a function of the sample holder temperature is presented as an example for an applied current of 0.1 A and for a measurement performed with a Specular Spin Valve (SV)³⁵.

The voltage across the sample and the thermocouple voltages ($TC1$, $TC2$, TCA , TCB) are instantaneously acquired at intervals of 2s. The Seebeck coefficient is instantly calculated to be the measured voltage divided by the instant temperature difference.

FIGURE 2: The applied temperature difference ΔT as a function of the sample holder temperature T . The inset shows the generation of ΔT by applying a constant current (0.1 A) to the resistance inside Block 1, changing its temperature $TC1$ to $T + \Delta T$. The temperature of the Block 2, $TC2$, is kept equal to T .

Quasi-steady differential measurements

Using this setup, quasi-steady differential measurements of the Seebeck coefficient can also be performed. The sample holder is kept at a constant temperature. Currents are applied to the heater resistance inside the copper block, increasing the temperature of that block while keeping the other block at the same temperature of the sample holder. The voltages and temperatures are simultaneously acquired while the applied current varies. In Figure 3.a) the temperature difference and the generated voltage are represented as a function of time during a quasi-steady measurement of the SV. Figure 3.b) presents the voltage across the SV as a function of ΔT at different temperatures. The Seebeck coefficient is calculated from the slope of the linear dependency of the voltage on the temperature difference, being also represented in Figure 3.b).

FIGURE 3: Seebeck coefficient measured by the quasi-steady differential method. a) Temperature difference and the generated thermoelectric voltage as a function of time. The voltage change due to a variation of the temperature difference is clearly visible. b) The Voltage across the sample as a function of the applied temperature difference. The expected linear relationship is observed.

2. Resistivity measurement

The resistivity is measured in a two-probe method. The current is fed through the two probes, each in each Block of Figure 1. The generated voltage is measured at the terminals of the probes. If a 4-probe measurement is necessary, an extension can be achieved by wire bonding two additional contacts into the sample. For measurements as a function of temperature, a constant current is applied. The current value is decided by considering that the generated power should not be higher than 500 mW and the resistance of the sample. The temperature is varied, either increasingly or decreasingly, at a rate of 0.5 K/min. The value of the voltage and temperature of the sample holder are acquired instantaneously every 2 s, corresponding to roughly acquiring values every 20 mK.

To verify the response of the system, different currents were applied to the SV sample. The measured voltage and the applied current as a function of time are represented in Figure 4.a), showing the linear response of the system, in accordance with Ohm-law. These are represented in Figure 4.b) for different temperatures.

FIGURE 4: I-V curve resistance measurement. a) Applied current and measured voltage as a function of time. The voltage change due to a variation of the current is visible. b) The I-V curve of a specular spin valve, namely the voltage across the sample as a function of the applied current difference. The expected linear relationship characteristic of an ohmic behavior is clearly observed.

III. Validation of the measurement setup and method

In order to study the reliability and accuracy of the experimental setup, Seebeck measurements were performed, using the dynamical differential method, of commercial niobium foil and of a Specular Spin Valve (SV), previously measured^{35, 36}.

A. Commercial Niobium foil

The $S(T)$ of the niobium foil (Alfa Aesar, 99.8% - metals basis, annealed) measured utilizing this setup is represented in Figure 5.a), as well as a reference measurement of a polycrystalline rod of niobium (> 99.99%) from John Matthey, annealed at 1100°C³⁷. At high temperature ($T > 150$ K), there is a total overlap between the measured and reference values. By further cooling the sample, the temperature dependence of the Seebeck coefficient follows the same trend, decreasing in magnitude and becoming positive until reaching a maximum of $\sim 0.7 \mu\text{V/K}$, and then decreasing until it has negative values again. The temperatures at which these behaviors occur for the reference sample are different from the ones obtained with this measurement setup. This can be due to different sample characteristics, namely the purity of the niobium measured³⁷ or the degree of oxidation in the samples annealed at different temperatures.

To characterize the contact resistance of the setup, the niobium foil resistance was measured using the setup and a four-probe arrangement as a function of temperature. From the four-probe measurement, the resistivity ρ_{Nb} of the niobium foil was obtained, and it is shown in the inset of Figure 5.b). The obtained values are in accordance with the expected commercial values. Having obtained the resistivity of the niobium foil, the contact resistance was calculated following equation (1),

where $R_{Nb@setup}$ corresponds to the resistance of the Niobium foil measured using the setup, R_{Nb} is the resistance of the niobium foil, l is the length between the two contacts of the setup (1.5 cm), and w and t are the width and thickness of the niobium foil. The obtained contact resistance is thus represented in Figure 5.b) as a function of temperature. A characteristic metallic behavior is observed, where the resistance decreases with cooling, being 4.04848Ω at room temperature. This value and the obtained behavior are in accordance with what is expected for a two-probe method using this type of contacts, namely the resistance of the two copper blocks.

$$R_{Contacts} = R_{Nb@setup} - R_{Nb} = R_{Nb@setup} - \rho_{Nb} \frac{l}{wt} \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 5: Measurements of the commercial niobium foil and contact resistance of the setup. a) Seebeck coefficient as a function of temperature of the commercial niobium foil obtained using the above described setup and compared with reference³⁷. b) Contact resistance of the described setup obtained by measuring the resistance of the niobium foil. The inset shows the resistivity of the niobium foil measured with a four-probe method as a function of temperature. The contact resistance was calculated using this measured resistivity.

B. Specular Spin Valve

The measured $S(T)$ of the Specular Spin Valve is presented in Figure 6.a), normalized to its value at 300 K. A comparison is performed with previous reported results³⁵. Both measurements have the same temperature dependence and the Seebeck coefficient values are in accordance with each other, showing that the described setup can be used to obtain precisely the Seebeck coefficient as a function of temperature. The temperature dependence of the resistivity was also obtained using this apparatus. It is represented as a function of temperature in Figure 6.b), normalized to its value at 300 K. Previously reported results are also presented in this figure³⁶. Like the Seebeck coefficient, both curves have the same temperature dependence characteristic of metals, with an increase of the resistance with heating, and the values of resistance measured by the setup within a 3% error of the reference values.

FIGURE 6: Measurements of the Specular Spin Valve. a) Seebeck coefficient normalized by its value at $S_0 = S(300 \text{ K})$ as a function of temperature of the Specular spin valve obtained using the above described setup and compared with reference³⁵, which was measured using manual made electric contacts and a differential method. b) Resistivity normalized by its value at $\rho_0 = \rho(300 \text{ K})$ as a function of temperature of the Specular spin valve obtained using the above described setup and compared with reference³⁶, which was measured using a standard 4 linear probe method.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a setup developed for measurements of the Seebeck coefficient and Resistivity of thin films as a function of temperature between 10 and 300 K was presented. The apparatus and measurement setup were fully described, as well as the different procedures employed to perform the measurements. The Seebeck coefficient is measured using a two-probe arrangement and either a dynamic or steady/quasi-steady differential method, where resistive heaters create the temperature differences. A full measurement between 10 K and 300 K of the Seebeck coefficient is achieved in 10 hours. The Resistivity is obtained using a two-probe arrangement, with a contact resistance between roughly 2 and 4 Ω . The results obtained of commercial (niobium foil) and previously measured material (Specular Spin Valve) have a great agreement (within 3%) with references measured using a more complex and time-consuming measurement technique and setup.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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